

Smithsonian Institution Position Description
Smithsonian Libraries and Archives (SLA)
Digital Imaging Technician
GS-1001-07

INTRODUCTION

The Smithsonian Institution is a diverse museum and research complex dedicated to the increase and diffusion of knowledge. The Smithsonian Libraries and Archives (SLA) provides authoritative information and innovative services for Smithsonian Institution researchers and curators, as well as scholars and the public worldwide, to further their quest for knowledge. SLA also serves as the institutional memory of a unique cultural organization and is responsible for ensuring institutional accountability. Through responsible collection management, preservation and digital technologies, SLA warrants broad and enduring access to the Libraries' and Archives' collections for all users.

The position is located within the digitization program of the Smithsonian Libraries and Archives (SLA), Smithsonian Institution. SLA's digitization program is responsible for creating digital surrogates of SLA analog collections materials as well as the description, management and curation of the resulting digital assets. The program periodically offers digitization services in support of similar activities for other units and partner organizations in compliance with unit mission and priorities. The purpose of this position is to create, describe, share and maintain high quality digital images from the Libraries and Archives collections.

Requires periodic donning of nitrile gloves, finger cots and masks. Requires recurring bending, crouching, stooping, stretching and reaching. Must be able to lift up to 45 lbs. on a regular basis.

This is a developmental position for the target position of Digital Imaging Technician GS-1001-08, JC# 114479. Upon satisfactory completion of qualifications/performance and at management's discretion, the incumbent may be advanced non-competitively to the target position. The incumbent must demonstrate the ability to satisfactorily perform at the higher-grade level in all aspects of the position which will be the primary basis for consideration for advancement via promotion. However, it must be noted that meeting these requirements does not entitle the incumbent to advancement as the following conditions should be met: satisfactory completion of career development and training requirements; assumption of the higher level duties; completion or attainment of all qualifications requirements; the availability of funds; and the decision of management to take the action.

MAJOR DUTIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Digital Image Production (70%)

Independently performs image capture for a variety of bound or loose cultural heritage materials using various specialized equipment and software. Independently performs quality

assurance activities through the inspection of new digital surrogates for compliance with SLA standards and makes recommendations for re-imaging or re-processing of legacy digital assets to conform to current practices and standards. Uploads resulting image files into the appropriate system of record for digital asset management, following SLA procedures, and ensures derivative files are made according to established guidelines. Ensures the security and safety of collection items by following policies on proper handling and environmental requirements before, during and after imaging. Coordinates and consults with conservators as needed, following Unit protocols. Maintains equipment, calibration, color profiles and other digitization configuration factors in accordance with schedule and specifications. Troubleshoots equipment and software issues, escalating unusual or highly technical problems to supervisor or team lead. Assists in monitoring digitization equipment and accessories for wear. Supports the maintenance of digitization accessories and recommends such items for replacement. Keeps dedicated digital imaging labs and any temporary or permanent designated digital imaging spaces clean and organized.

Metadata Generation and Enhancement (20%)

Prior to digitization, reviews existing descriptive metadata for SLA analog collections items to ensure minimum standards are met, and alerts supervisor to any missing information or errors. Creates and applies image-level (file level) descriptive, administrative and structural metadata within the system of record post-production following Unit standards. Reviews digital asset metadata application work, including for preexisting digital assets and/or vendor or rights holder supplied digital files, for standards compliance. Applies any routine corrections or seeks guidance regarding substantial errors. Applies metadata for more granular levels of the digital surrogate, for example descriptive information for specific pages/files within a compound digital object (such as articles within books, or pages within a diary). Such metadata are added into defined fields for specific groupings of digital surrogates. Adds digital surrogates to defined collections within systems of record to aid discoverability and access.

Programmatic Support Services (9%)

Meets deadlines for digital image creation, digital asset upload, metadata application and analog material movement. Adheres to digitization workflow requirements, seeking guidance for special circumstances. Maintains accurate inventory of collections materials at workspace. Responds to questions regarding such items. Communicates with staff points of contact related to dependent workflows and services, such as for preservation review or conservation treatments as well as for descriptive metadata corrections or enhancements for analog materials prior to imaging. Responds to questions from volunteers and interns regarding digitization and post-production procedures. Monitors user requests for digital imaging services and/or metadata services and completes requests in a timely manner. Promptly communicates when assignments are completed, and in any cases of unusual delay or if an assignment cannot be completed. Maintains relevance and accuracy of user request queues, editing requests for clarity and removing or closing any requests that are no longer active. Supports the creation and maintenance of workflow and policy documentation for activities of the SLA digitization program. Participates in planning for equipment replacement and lifecycle management, maintaining awareness of developments in imaging technologies, practices and

standards with application to cultural heritage digitization. Provides statistics for individual digitization work. Contributes to and authors informational documents for the public, in support of raising awareness of the collections and services of the Unit. Such documents may include blog posts, social media contributions and group presentations. Serves as a representative of the SLA digitization program at internal and external meetings and conferences.

Performs other duties as assigned (1%).

FACTOR DESCRIPTION

Factor 1 – Knowledge Required by the Position

Work requires knowledge of basic principles, concepts, and methodology for the identification, consideration and resolution of issues with the digital collection and digitization efforts. Problems within purview typically present themselves during operations or are reported by another party. Assignments do not require significant deviation from established methods and precedents such as performance and production standards and information on the collections, digitization equipment, and metadata specs. Camera work requires familiarity with the camera equipment used in assignments to produce acceptable work. Equipment used is specialized and work requires understanding the uses of a wide range of special purpose accessories, including different types of lenses and lighting sources. Metadata work requires knowledge of how to apply established techniques and practices, such as the application of descriptive information into defined fields.

Factor 2 – Supervisory Controls

The supervisor defines the incumbent's scope of responsibility and makes assignments by defining objectives, priorities and deadlines. The incumbent plans and carries out the successive steps of imaging (generally photographic) and metadata assignments. S/he independently solves commonly occurring technical problems, such as character encoding errors, digital artifacts and equipment malfunctions. The supervisor or more senior staff members provide more detailed assistance in unusual situations that do not have clear precedents and for metadata or imaging assignments that call for substantial departures from established procedures or standard imaging techniques. Completed work is evaluated for technical quality, appropriateness, conformity to policy and requirements and for meeting the objectives of an assignment. The methods used in accomplishing the work are not usually reviewed in detail.

Factor 3 – Guidelines

For digital imaging work, the format and content of the digital imaging (generally, photographic) assignment are specified and techniques and procedures for doing the work are established. Technical guides are available that provide detailed instructions on such matters as lens settings and exposure times to be used in taking routine digital images under normal conditions. For metadata work, guidelines include Unit standards and documentation for descriptive, administrative and structural metadata application. The guidelines provide

detailed instructions on such matters as applying page level metadata using a data dictionary and ensuring that descriptive metadata created by others are correctly associated with the digital surrogate within the system of record. The incumbent uses judgment in locating and selecting appropriate references and in making minor deviations in procedures to fit the specific assignment. Situations where precedents are not available or where procedures and methods must be substantially altered are referred to the supervisor or team lead for additional guidance.

Factor 4 – Complexity

Assignments typically involve a variety of still photography. The subjects to be photographed are specified, the extent of coverage is predetermined and the general format is established. Day-to-day work involves taking clear photographs to document objects, documents and images for SLA's digitization operations. The incumbent has discretion to determine the positioning, background, lighting, angles, distance and other aspects that will complement or enhance the subjects based on the intended use and audience for each image. Assignments require the use of different cameras, lenses, lens settings, lighting equipment and other accessories to produce images of acceptable quality. The incumbent identifies features that are difficult to photograph, such as reflective surfaces, fine or subsurface details, confined spaces or moving parts or that pose processing problems. The incumbent makes compensating adjustments in equipment and techniques. The metadata work involves familiarity with Unit standards and applying that knowledge to a course of action by selecting from many alternatives, including identifying and recommending minor deviations from established practices of the Unit.

Factor 5 – Scope and Effect

This position improves the efficiency and productivity of SLA and its digital assets. The incumbent identifies, analyzes and makes recommendations to resolve conventional problems and situations in workflow, work distribution, staffing, organizational structure and administration of digitization efforts. Collaborates with peers across SI and in industry to promote the highest rate of success in SLA and in the profession. Develops detailed procedures and guidelines to supplement established administrative regulations or program guidance, which are provided to lower-graded staff and contractors, or are used for solicitation of contract services. Completed work products influence SLA decisions concerning internal administrative operations.

Factor 6 – Personal Contacts

Contacts are typically with SI employees, supervisors and managers as well as those from federal agencies or non-federal organizations, both within the US and globally, with similar digital asset and digital imaging functions as part of SLA's participation in consortiums, projects, and other collaborative initiatives. Some contacts are with contract staff working collaboratively or under the incumbent's direction.

Factor 7 – Purpose of Contacts

Contacts are to provide advice to SLA and other managers on noncontroversial image digitization-related issues. The incumbent must identify decision-making alternatives, brief out on success in meeting goals and recommend solutions to persistent problems affecting SLA's digital assets.

Factor 8 – Physical Demands

The work is sometimes sedentary but does require long periods of standing or recurring bending, crouching, stooping, stretching and reaching. Must lift items up to 45 lbs. on a regular basis, such as boxes of books or journals, and moderately heavy equipment and materials.

Factor 9 – Work Environment

Work is typically performed in an adequately lit and climate-controlled office.